

On the Membranous Interface of the Material and the Spiritual (from an EPEMC perspective)

& Dual/Double Layer Economics... a proposed test of EPEMC's 'metallic' properties: tensile strength, malleability, durability

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July 2021

ABSTRACT

The world has grave economic problems. Whether from nonlinear dynamical or thermodynamical violations, it exists on the edge of derivatives meltdowns and currency wars¹. To discover a solution the author looks at means, motivation, and opportunity via a philosophy centered around the question 'what mediates the movement from the 'spiritual' into the material and back again?' This is the foundational paper of the MIMS series, where the concept of such an atomic-aetheric interaction is proposed. The Unified Aether Field is the Plasma-electromagnetic Force², and the place of this Force is also put into context with the other main powers, validated in form via Chinese Sciences and EPEMC cross comparisons. The UAF is able to help a PEM cosmologist formulate a visioning pathway for real, pragmatic solutions (so that philosophy is re-integrated to science). The purpose then, as it was for Nikola Tesla when he visioned the AC motor, is to take a much needed and desired fantasy and create a valuable reality (as opposed to destructive). Two forms of MIMS are discussed: one as simple as a grocery store visit, and the other a modern emergent technological career: the bitcoin/crypto miner. From there, the model for an emergent MIMS and its diagram is used, in comparison to the behaviors of Double Layers in PEMC, to discuss the proposition of a hypothesis for Dual Layer Economics. Emphasis in this paper is not upon long, western style dialectical philosophy, which would necessitate dozens more pages and lengthy discourse, but upon movement (propensity). This, the author feels, will yield more productive results in terms of getting to a hypothesis and justifying (via cross-comparison with PEMC and Chinese Sciences) practical expenses and efforts to make randomized trials to test the DLE hypothesis. Further papers are finally proposed in exploration of MIMS and DLE.

Keywords: cryptocurrency - materialism - spiritualism - double layer plasma - economics

¹ See: epilogue

² The search for the Unified Field has been hampered by most missing the obvious. If EMF doesn't need a medium to propagate... it is the aether everyone has been looking for. Not space-time, not strings, not dark matter, and not axions.

Synopsis

Science and Religion exist in a form of yin/yang polarity, with Science being truly endless, devoid of completion of fact, and ignorant but seeking endlessly; and Religion being self-contained, formed, slowly evolving (by generational gestalt in anthropological interaction with individuals), professing full knowledge (though each seems devoid of some knowledge others have) confident because of their solid basis in cosmological events (described in other papers). One can tell us nothing of how a person shall live rightly, and the other nothing of how the Universe and Nature work, save through a narrow homocentricity (and varying degrees of psychological insight: “human nature”). Yet they are unable to dispatch one another for they are both arising out of the same events and of very real human needs. Downstream of this tension is a very human concern: the material versus spiritual³ needs of the individual, society, and the entire world, especially in relation to the potential divine and the Universe at large.

In this paper the author shall explore this membranous interface, and the implications of it (and therefore our responsibilities, to ourselves, to each other, to the “divine⁴” etc.) in relation most specifically to the practical needs of a modern, semi-digital, fully globalizing economy, and to the individuals own search for purpose, meaning, happiness, livelihood, and utility within a growingly complex society.

After that the author will apply the concept with a proposed test, and a hypothesis, of a new concept based upon double layers in plasma: Dual Layer Economics (DLE™). A full explanation will be given to the high level of the concept, with some derivation of its necessity. A proposed demonstration of it put into action will be proposed (or indeed demonstrated), on the individual level. Finally in the conclusion, some circulation back to the central issue of the Membranous Interfacing of Material and Spiritual (MIMS) will be afforded, as a means to bring clarity to the utility and import of the subject.

Please note: the author’s background in both electrical engineering, math, and science is balanced here with clinical experience in Traditional Chinese Medicine, entrepreneurship, fatherhood, and hiking. But such colorations and biases are probably a bit inseparable. Furthermore, it is, to a degree, the author’s assertion that

³ The author sets aside his faith, and invokes a scientific form of spirit: mind/psyche, combined with emotional affection (and all concordant neurotransmission, as per modern biomedicine and the concepts of Charge Distributive Networks), and some form of soul, perhaps known to most as “identity.”

https://www.academia.edu/38098436/Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_structure_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models

⁴ Taken in EPEMC to be the continuous circulation of ‘aether’ which is so far defined as the sea of charge and baryons, but is not limited to this because of the separate but related concept of the author “two-way entropy” and the “spongy counterspace.” Bear in mind the axiom that the Unified Aether Field IS the Plasma-electromagnetism we already deal with, albeit in incomplete study and form, and hacked into many separate but actually related parts. If there is a consciousness (as the author suspects and can argue for), it is an emergent process of the networking of this circulating ‘divine’ energy, that appears to move itself via induction and the author’s concept of “Cosmic Rearrangement.” See: https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

Chinese Sciences⁵ (where they intersect with EPEMC^{6 7 8} and not superstition) will supercede in philosophy discussions, because they are wholly polar⁹, and not Cartesian, or Aristotlian, but are full Socratic, as proved by the Logician schools¹⁰. However, this bias will maybe alleviate some readers, and worry others (be they religious, or “rationalists”) who are leery of the bleedover of concepts. It would be wise, in guarding against the syncretism thereby presented¹¹, to review the previous paper on this issue, as well as review the purpose of EPEMC and all its philosophical implications for potentially new directions for mankind¹², for religion¹³, and for medicine¹⁴. If this is ignored, or if one continues on past this point, the author only asks for an open mind, if not blind acceptance of some concepts, as he is not a: nihilist, existentialist, solipsist, nor many other forms of limiting cults of mindset. A broad mind is both liberal and conservative, and it is this ‘spirit’ that he hopes the reader continues with. And he begs the pardon of those forms of ‘skeptics’ which are not really skeptical so much as full of doubt... because he will not spend much time educating them about their shortcomings, only encouraging the reading of the citations.¹⁵

MIMS

Traditionally, philosophical treatises, especially in the western strain, are lengthy, verbose derivatives. However, this will be philosophy-lite (so as to avoid a TLDR). In short, when we talk about the Material we mean 3 things:

1. Material/atomic/chemical goods and a material based existence
2. Material wealth (ie, money)
3. Consumerism

We may add to this the consumption of “material” (neurochemical release) of the following mundanities:

1. Entertainment & leisure (including snacking)
2. Sex
3. Drugs & other mind-altering substances (like sugar or caffeine)
4. Action (violence, anger, aggression, etc. which induce a certain response in the individual)
5. Media & social media (particularly images)

⁵ https://www.academia.edu/37784032/Chinese_Natural_Philosophy_Physics_in_EPEMC

⁶ https://www.academia.edu/36753648/Extended_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Cosmology_EPEMC

⁷

https://www.academia.edu/37569958/EPEMC_tm_Benefits_Ten_Reasons_to_Consider_Switching_to_Extended_Plasma_electromagnetic_Cosmology

⁸

https://www.academia.edu/40069702/The_Electric_Universe_Memo_For_Plasma_Electromagnetic_and_Diffusion_Catastrophic_Cosmologies_EPEMC_An_Electric_View_Community_Publication

⁹ “The Stone Monkey : An Alternative, Chinese-Scientific, Reality,” Bruce Holbrook, 1981

¹⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/School_of_Names

¹¹ An example would be of the author’s faith, which is both Christian and Quanzhen (complete reality) Taoist; or Christaioist. His favorite gospel, for example, is the Gospel of Thomas (the oldest gospel we think to have found).

¹²

https://www.academia.edu/38560727/Birkeland_Polyphase_Superweb_A_Proposition_for_the_Future_Betterment_of_Mankind_global_defense_interconnection_and_unlimited_power

¹³

https://www.academia.edu/38206009/Parameterization_of_New_Religion_utilizing_EPEMC_and_Western_Humanistic_Egalitarianism_as_a_guide

¹⁴

https://www.academia.edu/38098436/Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_structure_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models

¹⁵ Mankind needs spirituality, and now we know why

<https://scitechdaily.com/scientists-identify-specific-human-brain-circuit-for-spirituality/>

6. Music¹⁶

When we speak of the matters of the Spiritual, we particularly (but not only mean):

1. The religious
2. The psychologically affecting (particularly joy and happiness, and peace)
3. Metaphysical
4. Occult (superstitious powers), Oracles, etc.
5. Animistic and/or associated with trance

Where we see, then the most common interaction between the MS, creating a very obvious MIMS would be anywhere we most commonly see such exchanges happen:

- ❖ Churches & religious organizations
- ❖ Cults, communes, off-grid farms, etc.
- ❖ Government interactions with the church (tax status)
- ❖ Use of Mediums and medium like services
- ❖ Supplement marketing
- ❖ Book sales
- ❖ Music (and media) industry
- ❖ Hospitals and funeral services
- ❖ Etc.

There are, of course, numerous places which cannot be listed where a MIMS would be proposed to exist. For example, if a person has/builds a career, they are thoroughly wrapped up in that, and associated projects, energetically. When they are wrapped up in this career and/or project, they will have an interaction through the exchange of “wage” or “income” wherein the trade of the asset of time and of their chemical energy, as well as something far more tangible that affects their health, will be assessed by two or more parties at a material rate. This material rate is convertible to taxes and salary, which is then broken down into various forms of energetic but material use: groceries, bills, goods, entertainment etc. Some of these re-conversions will be negotiated against the entire household or personal budget, to create an exchange back into the Spiritual, such as leisure, or entertainment (commonly: streaming services and internet usage these days), music, outings, vacations, etc. which provide a healthy re-exchange or re-charge (people literally say “I need to recharge my batteries”) of Spiritual reserves¹⁷.

¹⁶ The ancient Chinese particularly abhorred the abuse and misuse of the “6 notes” and various forms of music, and its effects on the spiritual (mind). Many texts remark upon the music.

¹⁷ The author is not overly concerned with the potential offense (many have been throughout history) of a conscious Divine being reduced from analog in this discussion through the digital to a scientific domain because the MIMS is the primary focus, not the Spiritual perse, and the membrane is at least a partial mundanity. The mundanity creates a glossy interface, at best, wherein the limitations of words themselves to describe the ineffable is already an acknowledged religious problem. Most prophets and sages reverted to the use of simile, parable, and paradox to give meaning to that which the logical and everyday mind was unable to describe: Buddha, Yeshua, Laozi, Zhuangzi for example. In pre-Transitional Period texts we tend not to find metaphor but an alternate form of literal technicality which relies on gods, angels, demons, etc. But during the Transition Period, changes to more versatile subject matter (eg. “the serpent”) were required of mankind, as the gods were no longer concretely visible spheres but anthropomorphized cultural abstractions. Objects such as ‘vimanas’ ceased to be asteroidal objects but became abstract sky-faring vessels which could carry gods and powerful weapons. This sort of lossiness is typical of mediums of storage in the first place. Then add to that the limited number of neurons in a brain to describe the unlimited and indeed likely eternal and infinite Universe whose known or visible strata exceeds our neuron count easily, and whose scales of size defy our imaginations... well it is easy to see that the mundane is the limiter. Therefore in discussion of the MIMS, it will follow that all the subject matter can be forgiven a digital reduction from the analog perfection.

Traditional forms of capacitance into the Spiritual remain in effect, such as tithing. While tithing is seen by many cynics as a pure power/control mechanism of the Church, many people give as a form of charity, or relief of wealth-encumbrance (as it pertains to gluttony and guilt and greed¹⁸) and acknowledgment of good fortunes, etc., or a mere form of thanks to the Divine. The author himself makes use of the charity tray **and** follows the ancient Biblical recommendation of how to store and make more wealth via the 10% rule¹⁹. By utilizing a profit-first system the author devised a means to survive the COVID lockdowns for the service business, and actually to thrive²⁰.

Therefore, is it not also surmisable that there are as many potential MIMS surfaces as are needed, or requested?

A EPEMC definition for “GOD”

In a separate time and place, the author will step through a more mathematical (linear, algebraic) proof for the existence of a Creator. As it suffices in EPEMC (where the first E represents “extended”) the existence of a Creator God mytho-historically is unquestioned. It is something the entire world knew prior to the Transition Period and many thereafter as well. In fact the rise of atheism is still in such a vast minority, that it could almost be regarded as a mutant strain in the cultural DNA of mankind.

Nevertheless, the author feels compelled to borrow from the Chinese Sciences a schema that will

enable two neat discussions. First, a working PEMC definition for GOD (the supra-luminous web of plasma consciousness, wherein stars live and galaxies bear quasar-children, etc.), and that this must be a scientifically constrained, diagrammatic definition. Only after that a use of something from the Chinese Scientific study of “the Changes” (which for Judeo-Christians the passage of which is God’s Plan, etc.) can be used to illustrate something about the MIMS. The author must explain something, first, before presenting the diagram. The following figure illustrates what a taxonomical hierarchy is like:

How animals are classified

© 2015 Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.

Figure 1: Animal Classification

¹⁸ Interesting these, as well as God, all start with g.

¹⁹ Matthew 13:12 & 25:29

²⁰ This was not done without the help of the Divine, which again at a minimum is the great circulating web of energy from which we all partake. It was quite likely, mediated by consciousness greater than his own, but at least his own higher self was involved. The jury is out on if one’s Higher Self is divine, or merely an ideal we all know subconsciously, and imposed upon one another (eg. Justice, fairness, right and wrong, etc.).

It is easy to see here the reason why all apes are mammals, but not all mammals are apes. This is a given. Similarly, when discussing yin or yang, one cannot say yin = female and yang = male. This is not accurate. Yin is a category which includes negative, female, dark, moist, nurturing, essence, shady, protons, etc. Those are all very different categories of items. So female is not negative, or dark, etc. But all of these are yin. Yang is simply the polar reverse, but the same idea.

In this way the Chinese, observing the biological facts of chalice and phallus, designed the diagrams for yin and yang like so: yin = --- --- and yang = -----. In other words, yang is a solid line (typified by the erect penis, Te of the Great Man, or by "wood" like Oak trees, or metals, etc.) and yin is a broken line. Yang is penetrating, yin is receptive, etc. These are noncontroversial polar observations of the empirical world.

Switching from heteronormative and biological typology (which as it turns out presents an issue for this schema²¹) to philosophical or numerological schema, we will move out of the realm of male and female to concepts such as unification or division, or even 0 and 1, we can hopefully avoid the modern baggage and observe the following theology through the lens of the ancients, though it is a modern syncretic observation.

Figure 2: Wuxing Classifications²²; credit: Wikipedia

Figure 3: "The Big G"²³; credit: author²⁴

The oldest surviving text in the world is oft cited to be the I Ching (Zhou Yi), and therefore we can be forgiven to take these six yang powers that run the Universe, and assign them the 6 yang bars, and see if there is a correspondence with the most ancient mathematical text:

"1. Ch'ien / The Creative

above CH'IEN / THE CREATIVE, HEAVEN
below CH'IEN / THE CREATIVE, HEAVEN

The first hexagram is made up of six unbroken lines. These unbroken lines stand for the primal power, which is light-giving, active, strong, and of the spirit. The hexagram is consistently strong in character, and since it is **without weakness, its essence is power or energy**. Its image is

²¹ Males are XY and females are XX. XX would be more unified in concept than XY.

²² The center is also known as Earth; so if the 5 points of Jupiter South Pole changes to the 6 pointed star, as it did in November 2019, we may be permitted, theologically, to adjust the 5 phase diagram to a potential Star of David, OR, a hybrid diagram. Indeed the 6th point/vortex did form first in the center and then move to the outside.

²³ Lord can be mind-lord (Mind of Tao), or King, Jesus, Buddha, Horus,... insert your messiah here.

²⁴ For more about IAO, see author's paper: https://www.academia.edu/38744706/Uchell_the_High_Lord_and_Shang_Di

heaven. **Its energy is represented as unrestricted by any fixed conditions in space and is therefore conceived of as motion. Time is regarded as the basis of this motion.** Thus the hexagram includes also the power of time and the **power of persisting in time, that is, duration.**

The power represented by the hexagram is to be interpreted in a dual sense—in terms of its action on the universe and of its action on the world of men. In relation to the universe, the hexagram **expresses the strong, creative action of the Deity.** In relation to the human world, it denotes the creative action of the holy man or sage, of the ruler or leader of men, who through his power awakens and develops their higher nature.

THE JUDGMENT

THE CREATIVE works sublime success,

Furthering through perseverance.

According to the original meaning, the attributes [sublimity, potentiality of success, power to further, perseverance] are paired. When an individual draws this oracle, it means that success will come to him from the primal depths of the universe and that everything depends upon his seeking his happiness and that of others in one way only, that is, by perseverance in what is right.

The specific meanings of the four attributes became the subject of speculation at an early date. The Chinese word here rendered by “sublime” means literally “head,” “origin,” “great.” This is why Confucius says in explaining it: “Great indeed is the generating power of the Creative; all beings owe their beginning to it. This power permeates all heaven.” For this attribute in here is in the other three as well.

The beginning of all things lies still in the beyond in the form of ideas that have yet to become real. But the Creative furthermore has power to lend form to these archetypes of ideas. This is indicated in the word success, and the process is represented by an image from nature: “The clouds pass and the rain does its work, and all individual beings flow into their forms.”

Applied to the human world, these attributes show the great man the way to notable success: “Because he sees with great clarity causes and effects, he completes the six steps at the right time and mounts toward heaven on them at the right time, as though on six dragons.” The six steps are the six different positions given in the hexagram, which are represented later by the dragon symbol. Here it is shown that the way to success lies in apprehending and **giving actuality to the way of the universe [tao], which, as a law running through end and beginning,** brings about all phenomena in time. Thus each step attained forthwith becomes a preparation for the next. Time is no longer a hindrance but the means of making actual what is potential.

The act of creation having found expression in the two attributes sublimity and success, the work of conservation is shown to be a continuous actualization and differentiation of form. This is expressed in the two terms “furthering” (literally, “creating that which accords with the nature of a given being”) and “persevering” (literally, “correct and firm”). “The course of the Creative alters and shapes beings until each attains its true, specific nature, then it keeps them in conformity with the Great Harmony. Thus does it show itself to further through perseverance.” In relation to the human sphere, this shows how the great man brings peace and security to the world through his activity in creating order: “He towers high above the multitude of beings, and all lands are united in peace.”

... The attribute perseverance is correlated with wisdom, which discerns the immutable laws of all that happens and can therefore bring about enduring conditions. These speculations,

already broached in the commentary called *Wên Yen*, later formed **the bridge connecting the philosophy of the “five stages (elements) of change,”** as laid down in the *Book of History (Shu Ching)* with the philosophy of the *Book of Changes*, which is based solely on the polarity of positive and negative principles. In the course of time this combination of the two systems of thought opened the way for an increasingly intricate number symbolism.

THE IMAGE

The movement of heaven is full of power.

Thus the superior man makes himself strong and untiring.

Since there is only one heaven, the doubling of the trigram Ch'ien, of which heaven is the image, indicates the movement of heaven. One complete revolution of heaven makes a day, and the repetition of the trigram means that each day is followed by another. This creates the idea of time. Since it is the same heaven moving with untiring power, there is also created the idea of duration both in and beyond time, a movement that never stops nor slackens, just as one day follows another in an unending course. This duration in time is the image of the power inherent in the Creative.

*With this image as a model, the sage learns how best to develop himself so that his influence may endure. He must make himself strong in every way, by consciously casting out all that is inferior and degrading. **Thus he attains that tirelessness which depends upon consciously limiting the fields of his activity.*** (transl. Wilhelm-Baines)

Here we see that the concept is validated, first and foremost, but also the tithing concept (in terms of energetic expense and time expense) and the rest is validated. By consciously limiting the fields of activity, one rests. By resting, power is enabled to flow.

Back to Figure 3, we see that the Force (PEM or Tao) is set opposite and able to control the phase position of the Principles (or Laws of Meta-Physics: Causality, Flux/Evolution, Relativity, Conservation, Vibration, Rotation, Polarity, and Resonance). It depends on the Heavenly Aether or Sea of Charge, because PEM=UAF. All of these rely on the power of Numbers for mathematical consistency and calculation (consider celestial mechanics and quantum mechanics)... and the Lord would be the one omnipotently able to alter any of these, at will.

So the diagram is self-consistent, and governed by the Wuxing properties already cited in other papers and from ancient times, seen on the south pole of Jupiter (and we saw this as surely as we saw the North Pole of Jupiter²⁵ and perceived the Fibonacci sequence, and found the Ba (8) gua).

Good, self-consistency is important in any framework. EPEMC is now in phase, pun intended, with the Chinese Sciences (and incidentally the Egyptian Sciences²⁶). The outcome is this: we are able to discuss the MIMS in the terms of EPEMC and realize that there is, and always has been, a consistent theological concern with the material and as it concerns the spiritual. There is an interface of these two subjects of Material and Spiritual, and it is not a pithy matter, neither in “alchemy” (transmutation of reality) nor in modern day consumerism and capitalistic economies²⁷.

²⁵

https://www.academia.edu/38755475/Hopewellian_Octagons_Proof_that_the_Allegewi_Astronomers_could_see_Jupiter_up_close_Analysis_of_the_Octagon_formation_of_Chillicothe_and_Newark_Earthworks

²⁶ This is not to be taken lightly because they had much more architectural and numerological success than any other early Megalithic culture.

²⁷ In fact, it is precisely this reality which has been used to study things from the vice-ridden Roman Empire and its subsequent downfall, to the riches of Solomon, and then more recently the failings of the virtue-eschewing Communism which takes a form of looting out of Marxism, ignoring human nature just as they did at Plymouth Rock and Jamestown and creating miserable famine conditions, and combines it with an anti-spiritual tyranny of the State. The results were, of

The MIMS

*'Twas brillig, and the slithy toves
Did gyre and gimble in the wabe:
All mimsy were the borogoves,
And the mome raths outgrabe.
~Lewis Carrol, Jabberwocky*

Tis brillig indeed, when we look to work on the interface of yang (-----) and yin (--- ---). For indeed now that we know the yang accords to the Spiritual realm, and the yin accords to the Material realm, we can then map this interface. But we cannot rely on the polarity of one atop the other, nor can we use the Tian-Ren-Di trigram setup (3rd layer²⁸), because the “mankind” or consciousness level has an argument for both yin and for yang. Fortunately, the I Ching has an answering diagram for this:

64. *Wei Chi / Before Completion*

above LI / THE CLINGING, FLAME

below K'AN / THE ABYSMAL, WATER

This hexagram indicates a time when the transition from disorder to order is not yet completed. The change is indeed prepared for, since all the lines in the upper trigram are in relation to those in the lower. However, they are not yet in their places. While the preceding hexagram offers an analogy to autumn, which forms the transition from summer to winter, this hexagram presents a parallel to spring, which leads out of winter's stagnation into the fruitful time of summer. With this hopeful outlook the Book of Changes come to its close.²⁹

The author needs not speculate on the convenience, or consistent planning, of the Zhou Yi to begin with #1 and end with #64, and be also consistent with our own analysis.

The above two lines belong to Heaven, in that the button yin bar represents the Spiritual ability to respond to mankind (through such a mimsy as prayer). The bottom two lines belong to Earth in that inside the Earth is receptive to the sun and “hollow” (spherical shells³⁰), but at the surface the ground is hard (and this is not accidental, either in Creationism or in electro-geology). The middle then, is not really corresponding to something socially based, such as the yang is on top because of the patriarchy, etc. Rather, it is to correspond to the energy centers and biology of the body: the psyche is housed above in the head and heart, and the orifices of waste release, and sources of many people's cravings (and subsequent corruptions) are in the lower portions of the torso. Therefore we see a consistency of the concept that the yang line descends energy to the receptive “broken” line³¹. Note that at the end of this hexagram, it returns to #1 (Ch'ien), indicating a consistency of the MIMS diagram here.

Of course well known are the catastrophes of the Cultural Revolution, Great Leap Forward, and Bolshevism and Stalinism. Even more recently: Zimbabwe and Venezuela. Deaths in the hundreds of millions provide a concrete proof of concept.

²⁸ Also called samsara in Buddhism, with sam meaning 3. The threefold world is literally 3 dimensional reality.

²⁹ http://www.pantherwebworks.com/i_ching/bk1h53-64.html#64

³⁰ See the HEGEME theory in the PEMS paper previously cited.

³¹ This is consistent with Judeo-Christianity values wherein mankind is considered “broken” without the Lord, which as one sees in Figure 3 there is a correspondence with Fire or enlightenment. Please note the Fire plasmascript in Figure 2 is the Great Man, or Shang Di, and a **direct reference** to plasma.

https://www.academia.edu/38590072/Shang_Di_Heaven_and_Dao

To summarize the consistent pattern of the MIMS:

Is this consistent with the Taoist concept of “put the female on top”? This is a concept of being receptive first, rather than forceful, so as to effect wu wei, a concept of non-empty-inaction similar as per the Gita’s “Yoga of Action.” The idea is beyond the discussion here, but sufficient to say some in the circles of FLOW hypothesis³² or “in-the-zone” for sports circles, have noted that material wealth and success may be determined by timing and flexibility more than knowledge, talent, or even luck. This may have some support in the Chinese pseudoscience of feng-shui, but does not connect only tangentially to electrogeology³³. But we digress.

The consistency in question is if the MIMS should be the inverse of the proposed diagram? The answer is, even in Taoism as all religions, and in chemistry, resoundingly “no.” Energy gradients flow downwards, from higher concentrations to lower... but the well of energy of the Void flows “up” (or out). The mind also should be contained in the upper energy centers primarily, and not the lower to avoid destructive addictions, etc.

Furthermore, we can make test of this by comparing later in the DLE. But first, let us consider a few common real world examples. Can this interface describe a mundane experience such as a trip to the grocery store? Yes, perhaps a portion of it.

First we should examine the causes of the trip. The body runs on sugars particularly for the blood, muscle, and nervous system, as well as all tissues. The existence of the *need* for sugar in the body to create ATP is an established fact, but the remaining question is, “Why is blood sugar so vital at a certain level for the mediation of consciousness, let alone the facility of movement in a real, material world?” This is a very interesting philosophical question, but on a practical level we know that a person with changes in blood sugar have the following symptoms:

Table 1 - Glycemic Issues

Hypoglycemia ³⁴	Hyperglycemia ³⁵
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sweating ● Palpitations ● Foggy-headedness ● Tremulousness ● Anxiety ● Hunger ● Confusion ● Fatigue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Drowsiness ● Lethargy ● Delirium ● Seizures ● Visual disturbance ● Hemiparesis ● Sensory Defects ● Coma

The effects on the left ,which prompt hunger, which then necessitate the trips to restaurants and the grocery store, and affect the types of food decisions that are made, are quite pronounced. Yet the symptoms on the right are quite a bit more severe. So that which stabilizes consciousness or the spirit, vis-a-vis the blood sugar response is also potentially able to destroy it. Therefore we see that the most important MIMS interaction here is that the material which is the below substrate (yin) will interact with the yang or above layer

³² <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-flow-2794768>

³³ Leylines, dragons, etc... see the author’s papers showing the lichtenburgs of the Knobs of Kentucky, and see the Trip Reports, and see what happened to the drone used for photographing at Culvertown!
https://www.academia.edu/49439216/Trip_Report_Culvertown_Platform_Addendum

³⁴ <https://www.touchendocrinology.com/diabetes/journal-articles/hypoglycemia-and-the-central-nervous-system/>

³⁵

<https://www.medscape.com/answers/1914705-6659/what-are-the-neurologic-symptoms-of-hyperosmolar-hyperglycemic-s-tate-hhs>

in the CNS. The interaction is cumulative, and networked, but how is this MIMS manifesting? There is a physical need, a demand, and there is then a *desire*, which then mediates a prompt for an action of either preparation or immediate consumption. The weaker the ATP volume, the stronger the desire and prompt for consumption. The desire alters the decision processes. Whereas before the hunger signal rose upwards from the PNS and ENS into the CNS³⁶ there would have been thoughts predominating on any number of subjects, afterwards the mind is almost certainly dominated by thoughts of food. Forgetting how the thoughts even precipitate in the form of *preference* for sugars, fats, or proteins, or for particular flavors and vitamins, minerals, etc. the sheer fact that there is a substrate occurrence is why we are interested. There is something very interesting about the emergent response of the *network* of cells, and bundles of energy that are working on a quantum to molecular scale, to induce behaviors on the next scale, and so on and so forth. This response goes again from a material or atomic level, in the interaction of fields and valence shells, upwards towards a more unifying top-down hierarchy.

This may have larger implications for how or even why life might exist in the Universe: to mediate the lower level responses of energy gradients towards facilitating some upper level response on a global, solar system, galactic, and supragalactic scale³⁷. This isn't that surprising, since we see that in trees the pattern for life is like this: the roots bringing together lots of sources of nutrients towards a larger and larger structure. Not unlike how streams gather in creeks, into rivers, lakes, and seas, before becoming the Ocean. The Ocean here may represent GOD, if again GOD is a collective network of circulating energy.

This mediated experience of the emergent, which goes from the measurable needs of an energy network on a molecular level, into the desire that then precipitates a neurotransmitter signal that then propagates upwards from the stomach into the nervous system, is marvelous. But is it a unique MIMS?

The thought experiment is not concluded yet. Once the items are chosen, the skilled consciousness mediates the compulsion for instant gratification, then guides the starving body juiced with chemicals increasing desire and hunger, and moves it to the checkout. At the checkout there is a macro level exchange for chemicals (that hopefully taste good and indicate their nutritious value) with monetary energy. The chemical has been explored, and after all the reader probably can understand how they can memorize favorite foods, and carry around preferences, etc. But, the next level of interest is how there is an agreed upon exchanging rate for nutrients (measured in mass, usually ounces), and money. But money itself is interesting because physical atoms or digital numbers are used to represent this exchange, and it can be mediated between sales of goods, or even of money itself. How was this system invented? How did the concept move worldwide and become so commonplace?

Clearly many cultures and societies have found money useful. Typically they represented it with some precious metal, or pearls, beads, etc. Next most common was paper money which then due to convenience became the most common medium. So the desire for convenience now enters into the equation. The next level is digital, which is based upon the Force itself and the power of Numbers (via calculation, and memory). Memory is actually also an important topic in MIMS. We have, for example, the memory inherent to the medium such as the written and agreed upon value on the paper bill. Or, we have digital storage mediums. Nevertheless, memory is also a matter of consciousness as well. Is there a connection? Memory probably deserves its own paper, and is beyond this discussion.

So now that we are at the checkout, the body is commanded by the consciousness to scan the food (using the Force, via lasers) and calculate its value (again through electronic computing), and then the cashier refuses any bodily urges to steal or consume the nutrients, and then takes the money from the customer, and

³⁶ Peripheral, Enteric, and Central Nervous systems, respectively.

³⁷ See Table 7, p34 for an example of the electrical currents of scale in this schema

https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC

refuses the desire to steal this money which could procure nutrient sustenance. The cashier can do this because the consciousness is above the body and regulates it, and informs the body that later there will be a cash reward. However, the incentive to actually obey this command is mediated by the Spirit or psyche which explains to itself, and memorizes the concepts of justice, fairness, and criminality... in essence morality.

So what is the MIMS surface here? It is a lot more subtle than the earlier substrate between chemical need to desire, going from yin up to yang. Here the exchange is about yin, but is from yang (numbers) to business, which is motivated by profit, which is sort of yin. *Consumption* is definitely yin³⁸, and businesses have to consume to exist and to accumulate. But actual accumulation or conglomeration is also considered yin. Therefore, what is the medium of exchange? It seems it is agreement, which is a social level construct. It cannot be brought into the purely mundane realm the way that chemistry allows for nutrification. So what is agreement?

Let us skip long discourses of sociology, psychology, and the rest, leaving it for others. Instead, let us consider the definition of a "field." Fields are an ancient plasmaglyphic concept whose rice patty-like organizational structure actually refers directly to the Saturnian sun. As it happens, we use the word in science to describe *relationships* between the poles. Energy, force, pressure... all can be translated (or not) through the mediumship of the field between poles or relational partners.

Figure 4 - 田 Tian (homonym for heaven) "field" etymology revealing plasmascripts in the Liushitang; credit: hanziyuan.net³⁹

Working back to agreement, there is a real, tangible relationship and field dynamic. The buyer of the groceries is at a socially accepted *disadvantage*. They are not being purely moral... many people engaged by their animal consciousness shoplift or loot every day. But there is, for those with higher IQ and EQ measurements, an exponential decrease in propensity to commit crimes⁴⁰, and instead to find clever means of arbitrage of conflict.⁴¹ In other words, it is easy for the human engaged in a satisfactory level of happiness and cooperation, not under duress or driven by hunger and desire, etc. to control their impulses, to recognize the disadvantage of crime, and to *willingly* offer the paper medium of energetic storage for the purchase to the cashier.

³⁸ Yin and Yang: produce one another, consume one another, control one another, complete one another, and are infinitely divisible because they contain one another.

https://www.academia.edu/37784032/Chinese_Natural_Philosophy_Physics_in_EPEMC

³⁹ <https://hanziyuan.net/#%E7%94%B0>

⁴⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4525433/>

⁴¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4664650/>

The cashier recognizes they are not the owners of either the food nor the money, and they can command the catalytic exchange between the amorphous business entity and the hungry person. This graded relationship is complex, and could be diagrammed, but the basic idea is that it is a hierarchical relationship of convenience, peace (and therefore efficiency and safety), and mutual profit. The buyer then takes the food with them for immediate availability, and with far less risk than a hunt or crime, and less time than scavenging in the forest. The MIMS is more complex, and yet more beneficial (so it would appear at this time), than the previous MIMS. The more spiritual-abstract, the more beneficial? Perhaps that should be tested through many other thought experiments, in someone else's paper. For now we can just assume that it isn't of prime importance for exploration.

So what other kind of [hopefully not too complex] MIMS can we explore? How about the stock market? As much as the author wishes to delve into this, as it does touch the Power of Numbers, it seems to miss the power of the Principles, unless we wax philosophic about the Law of Supply & Demand. We should probably stick to the discourse of physics and the divine, for the moment.

What kind of mundane structure engages in an obvious or overt MIMS with both physics and the divine, without resorting to those domains for source material (theology and physics/chemistry)? We would rather avoid circular reasoning! Fortunately, in a more obvious way, cryptocurrencies themselves are reliant on both. Stock markets are also digital, but not obviously so to people, for they are reliant on the foundational monetary and financial valuation of businesses. That is a bit too complex. Cryptocurrencies provide an excellent test of the MIMS, if there is a way to actually prove a connection of consciousness, etc.

Cryptic Mimsy

First the audience should learn what a cryptocurrency, like Bitcoin, is precisely. It is a storage of monetary value, just as paper money or gold, (although at present its convenience is not as good as paper), based upon mathematical algorithms called blockchains, which are encrypted (scrambled). Its value is fourfold:

1. It is a verifiable, safe transactional medium, which can also be used for sending other digital values; as it is used its value goes up.
2. It is a currency market, and rather large. Before the recent China-induced crash, one "joke" coin alone was worth more than the entire Ford Motor Company.⁴²
3. It is a limited supply which can be infinitely divided for unlimited demand.
4. It is a means of decentralizing currency and increasing resiliency - so long as access to the PEM remains; for it is "mined" and "proof of work" done on internet networks. This is the key point we wish to dive into.

There are half a dozen more things worth saying about cryptocurrencies and Bitcoin which may or may not be relevant for our mimsical fancies. [But 'twould not be brillig to dash off into every forest and leave the field of discussion!] What is important here, for the reader especially (and not the already 'cup-is-full' economists relying on hyperinflating fiat to save fiat⁴³, violating thermodynamics!) is the personal MIMS. We shall approach it not from the perspective of an end user (app user or investor), or a money maker at a firm, but a crypto miner.

A crypto miner takes the aforementioned storage of monetary energy, earned through Work (energy / time) and through chemical mediation as previously described, and makes a purchase (online usually). They select equipment that is designed, best as possible, to perform routine mathematical calculations best suited to

⁴²

<https://www.marketwatch.com/story/the-cryptocurrency-dogecoin-began-as-a-joke-and-now-its-worth-more-than-ford-11618923488>

⁴³ <https://voxeu.org/article/feds-quantitative-easing-boost-investment-burden-inflation>

“mining.” At this time, ASIC miners are the preferred method⁴⁴, replacing GPUs which replaced CPUs⁴⁵. Each new evolution is geared more and more towards a specified purpose. This is already having a global macro economic impact of subverting chip manufacture⁴⁶, creating problems for auto and PC makers⁴⁷, as there is a true bottleneck in the chip making industry.⁴⁸

The miner does not worry about this, because they are willing to pay for their coming reward with a hope of a Return on Investment (ROI) that is purely digital, and separate from fiat. They can mimsically exchange crypto for fiat at any number of exchanges like Coinbase or Kucoin. But on the blockchain itself they hope to produce, as if out of thin air, the “coins” or “tokens” that they choose, and believe have the brightest future for widespread use in #1 to #3 above. Some even consider the sociopolitical ramifications of #4. But, in the end, all are interested in one thing: ROI.

This ROI is intriguing because it would, at first, appear to also violate thermodynamics as fiat does. But actually we note it does not. It comes at the literal expense of electricity usage. There is a typical desire to pay for electricity at a rate of no more than \$0.12 / kWh. To get below \$0.10 is also considered key⁴⁹. Why? Because the value increases per mined coin. Also, if there is a coin that not everyone is mining but is quite popular, maybe having some function as do Nonfungible Tokens (NFTs) like etherium (ETH), then all the better as for principle #1. So we have here a meeting membrane of the laws of physics (computational speed, thermodynamic efficiency, costs, physical limitations of chemistry and engineering issues like planned obsolescence, material dynamics, etc.), of the power of Numbers in its most raw form mankind has ever designed⁵⁰, and of personal use and intersection of whim/interest and pragmatism (such as consumer purchases, or homes⁵¹, cars⁵², etc.)

All of this is being performed *in the mining equipment* (as a single layer), which is mediating this MIMS. How? The yang (electricity) is contained within or beneath the physical electronics and software! That would appear to violate our diagram. However, if we look closely, we have a complex MIMS:

Figure 5; proposed Crypto MIMS; author⁵³

Note that the ROI is yin because it relates to material wealth and consumerism; and the purchase is an action (yang) but of something in the material realm (yin, especially relative to electricity and spirit).

The author is fairly satisfied with this. A later MIMS₂ paper may be done on cryptocurrency alone describing both the emergent process and the DLE aspect, in which multifaceted interactions are proposed and hopefully gaps to public use/acceptance are identified/predicted and can be taken advantage of monetarily well ahead of the usual emergent process. Already, though, as crypto relies so heavily upon the Power of Numbers and of the Physics/Principles and of the Force (PEM)... it is evolving very fast into realms of passive income, gambling, gaming/play, home economics, etc. The network aspect gives it tremendous power and

⁴⁴ <https://itigic.com/what-are-asics-for-mining-will-they-end-up-replacing-gpus/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.trymining.com/pages/asic-vs-gpu>

⁴⁶

<https://www.fxempire.com/forecasts/article/bitcoin-mining-adds-to-existing-shortage-in-semiconductor-market-chip-prices-surge-712458>

⁴⁷ <https://www.cnbc.com/2021/05/07/chip-shortage-is-starting-to-have-major-real-world-consequences.html>

⁴⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AeN3oQx-o68>

⁴⁹ <https://digiconomist.net/bitcoin-energy-consumption/>

⁵⁰ While designed, the ability of crypto to take off is an emergent process in response to the 2008 financial meltdown. A more detailed treatise on the history of digital currencies can be found here:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=W15A7Lf0_fl

⁵¹ <https://www.rockethomes.com/blog/home-buying/buy-house-with-bitcoin>

⁵² <https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-56508568>

⁵³ Please note the importance of this MIMS' diagram when we get to DLE.

rapid flux/evolution, again as the Law of Flux (Evolution) sits opposed to the Law of Rotation (wind and thunder are both electricity related).

Dual (or Double) Layer Economics

In the following section the DLE is derived, and proposed, with first the Double Layer Plasma (DLP) and after that the proposed pragmatic schemata and foundational theses upon which DLE can be based and built into its own series of not only papers but designs and experiments.

The Emerging Need for Global Economic Justice

The author has little time and space herein to rail against the obvious downsides of crony and vulture capitalism⁵⁴. Nor to extoll why it is obvious to cooperation leads to better function and economy than destructive forms of competition.⁵⁵ Unfortunately, without proposed alternatives to these anti-main street and mom-n-pop small business and centralizing and corrupting influences which unbalance stable western democracies, people are resorting to the fairytale promises of even more debase, morally bankrupt socialism, cultural marxism, and even proven defunct and debunked communism. The most recent COVID/Wuhan400⁵⁶ fiasco, from the weaponization of gain-of-function research from WHO/CDC⁵⁷ to the not-so-veiled bid for global economic power through asymmetric warfare by the Chinese Communist Party⁵⁸, to the subsequent coverups and political machinations of leftists and leftist sympathizers reveals that there is a great shortage of new ideas, and a great plethora of rich, connected players who are willing to push the Great Reset agenda⁵⁹, and a cashless society, in order to enrich themselves, more than help the planet. Doesn't stop them from couching it in phoney Climate Change terms^{60 61}... nevertheless, it is morally bankrupt⁶² and doomed to fail by any nonlinear dynamics analysis⁶³. The economy is too globalised, too complex, too digitized, and there are too many emerging markets on the internet alone, including the dApp and DeFi markets but not only those, for such an extending power to work. The likely outcome will be many civil wars, revolutions, and destruction to infrastructure, at a time when we can least afford it considering the actual facts of Solar-induced Climate Change (SICC)⁶⁴.

Secondly, when one considers the primary desire of humans it is to be individual-conscience, tribal, collective-conscious, and yet nationally patriotic. The primary mode for this for a time was the village, then city-state, then kingdom. When it became imperial it went too far both in terms of deaths of innocent civilians, and reach of economic destruction. So how can a One World Government (OWG) run by a New World Order (NWO⁶⁵), facilitated by a "deep state" socialist takeover of the current world superpower, the United States, and

⁵⁴ <https://www.theatlantic.com/politics/archive/2012/07/which-flavor-capitalism-do-you-prefer-crony-or-vulture/325761/>

⁵⁵ https://web.archive.org/web/20150420144847/http://www.princeton.edu/mudd/news/faq/topics/Non-Cooperative_Games_Nash.pdf

⁵⁶ "They call the stuff 'Wuhan-400' because it was developed at their RDNA labs outside of the city of Wuhan, and It was the four-hundredth viable strain of man-made microorganisms created at that research center".

<https://www.reuters.com/article/uk-factcheck-coronavirus-koontz-book/party-false-claima-1981-book-predicted-the-corona-virus-2019-outbreak-idUSKCN20M19I>

⁵⁷ <https://www.wsj.com/articles/anthony-fauci-and-the-wuhan-lab-11622759752>

⁵⁸ <https://www.c4i.org/unrestricted.pdf>

⁵⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0mpsr03s5pl>

⁶⁰ <https://www.weforum.org/great-reset/>

⁶¹ <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/africa-in-focus/2021/04/07/climate-adaptation-and-the-great-reset-for-africa/>

⁶² <https://thehill.com/opinion/energy-environment/504499-introducing-the-great-reset-world-leaders-radical-plan-to>

⁶³ <https://www.wsj.com/articles/the-failed-experiment-of-covid-lockdowns-11599000890>

⁶⁴ <https://theconversation.com/theres-always-the-sun-solar-forcing-and-climate-change-1878>

⁶⁵ <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/1992-03-01/what-new-world-order>

NATO allies in the EU, by the CCP⁶⁶ or does anyone else lead to anything different? It is contrary to human nature, and to reason. It is also contrary to Tesla's warnings that we must continue the great sociological work of "Increasing Human Energy."⁶⁷ World population reduction and other UN backed ideas like the Great Replacement⁶⁸, really do not deal with the facts of capitalism's "achilles heel": growth. It is unreasonable to expect infinite growth on a finite surface, without say subsurface fractal housing designs, under ocean subsurface cities, or space urbanization. Nevertheless, none of these movements have *any* traction whatsoever. They are, at best, pipe dreams of science fiction writers, or perhaps the hopes of idealists and dreamers for a time 10,000 years in the future. By then the population reduction will come anyhow through Nature's "swift kick in the pants" axiom⁶⁹. As mentioned in a previous paper of the author, the chances of a grade 6, 7, or 8 cataclysmic event are too high to wait, idly⁷⁰.

Therefore, the solution seems obvious. Avoiding a discussion of the politics involved in allowing people to govern themselves in small kingdom-like fiefs that are both modern and held to an enforceable standard of human rights, and to not abuse their neighbors... we do need to allow for a more resilient system of nation-states which are racially and culturally just (to prevent Rwanda or Palestine like situations), and economically viable. Even small nation states like Greece have been capable of producing worldwide economic catastrophes⁷¹! Spain, in many ways, is such a country of many countries⁷². Yet it also produced a not-so-minor catastrophe. Centralization might seem an anti-dote, but this is not exactly clear to the author as true, given the Chinese style Capitalism is a mere shell for black market corruption⁷³, fake GDP⁷⁴, and human rights abuses!⁷⁵

Crony capitalists in the west laud it and pay media corporations⁷⁶ to print pro-Chinese propaganda⁷⁷, but emerging individual markets worldwide don't seem to agree and are routinely seeking non-corporate media for news, and decentralizing the stories. The internet, in other words, is already a series of massive fiefdoms, and if anything physical strata such as developed infrastructure, is falling apart⁷⁸ ⁷⁹ as energies shift to online battlegrounds and markets! This is woefully similar to the communist dystopias⁸⁰, if not in scale but in form. The results are still the despondence of otherwise connected, option-laden youths who do not realize how well they have it⁸¹, and ironically chastise their freedoms (by using freedom to do so), and even commit violence and demand more freedom (paradoxically!) It's an emergent process caused by a lack of praxis between a digital emergent process which is wholly, if not holy, connected to the PEM, which is juxtaposed to the centralizing

⁶⁶ <https://www.nbr.org/publication/chinas-vision-for-a-new-world-order-implications-for-the-united-states/>

⁶⁷ <http://aetherwizard.com/tesla/Articles/ProblemOfIncreasingHumanEnergy.pdf>

⁶⁸ <https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/publications/ageing/replacement-migration.asp>

⁶⁹ "Beatings will continue until morale improves."

⁷⁰

https://www.academia.edu/38560727/Birkeland_Polyphase_Superweb_A_Proposition_for_the_Future_Betterment_of_Mankind_global_defense_interconnection_and_unlimited_power

⁷¹ <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/investing/070115/understanding-downfall-greeces-economy.asp>

⁷² https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=heCsx4t_K08

⁷³ https://www.ide.go.jp/library/English/Publish/Periodicals/De/pdf/98_01_02.pdf

⁷⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G632a6M2hC0>

⁷⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WS8UyTwAC5o>

⁷⁶

<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/world/china/ccp-buys-media-influence-by-paying-millions-to-us-dailies-magazines-report/articleshow/84109897.cms>

⁷⁷ <https://www.theatlantic.com/politics/archive/2020/05/china-disinformation-propaganda-united-states-xi-jinping/612085/>

⁷⁸ <https://www.dhs.gov/xlibrary/assets/st-aging-infrastructure-issues-research-technology.pdf>

⁷⁹

https://publications.iadb.org/publications/english/document/The_Impact_of_Digital_Infrastructure_on_the_Sustainable_Development_Goals_A_Study_for_Selected_Latin_American_and_Caribbean_Countries_en_en.pdf

⁸⁰ <https://archive.org/details/TheGulagArchipelago-Threevolumes>

⁸¹ <https://www.businessinsider.com/millennials-lives-compared-to-gen-x-baby-boomers-2018-3?op=1>

powers of oligarchs and NGOs⁸², which like as not some of which **still** have connections to the Saturnian “Divine Right to Rule” paradigm⁸³! How antiquated! How dilapidated!

To make it worse, each nation-state has every right to demand to manufacture their own currency, and yet as we see with Zimbabwe and Venezuela, this is not always a good thing for the people⁸⁴. As weak as the U.S. Dollar is, everyone else’s currency is weaker, including China’s! They are fighting the crypto movement to save the Yuan but it will not work, because they do not want to mediate with cryptocurrency, only take advantage of its tyrannical benefits (NFTs enable tracking). This won’t work out long term for the CCP or the world. The world signal is 8 billion people. That’s too much for the U.S. or China or the E.U. to control.

So what is the solution of how to have a protected internal currency, and a medium of interaction with the globalized system of currencies and stock market exchanges? Possibly, if the author is correct, the DLE!

What is a Double Layer in PEM?

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Understanding Double Layers: Part 1 Mechanisms & General Properties

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Figure 6 - Double Layers in Plasma (DLP); credit: G. Samuel (See the Pattern)⁸⁵

1. Current Carrying Streaming Electron
2. Current Carrying Positive ion
3. Trapped electrons on the downstream side of the steaming electrons
4. Trapped ions on the downstream side of the streaming ions

⁸² Non-governmental Organizations, typically having a lot of power, like the World Bank or IMF
⁸³

https://www.academia.edu/38993303/Caer_Melyn_Camelot_Cosmic_Hillfort_of_the_King_The_Yellow_Hill_fort_as_a_Cosmic_Hill_or_mountain_motif_and_symbol_of_a_Kings_authority

⁸⁴ <https://www.investors.com/politics/editorials/zimbabwes-coup-venezuelas-default-and-the-ongoing-failure-of-socialism/>

⁸⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3fggvOI9aEo>

“The streaming electrons and ions are present because the field-aligned current is an essential ingredient of a double layer. Due to the acceleration of the streaming particles by the Double Layer potential, the density of each streaming particle population decreases on the downstream side. Therefore, trapped particles must be produced to ensure overall charge neutrality.” ~G. Samuel⁸⁶

Is this not already a perfect description of why black and hidden markets come to populate even in healthy financial markets such as the United States (pre 2005)? The current carriage between financial and credit markets, i.e. between businesses (and their stocks and bonds) and banks (and their derivatives and loans), is buffered with a healthy amount of trapped wealth. These “trapped particles” of currency necessitate black market tools to mediate neutrality and achieve a form of equilibrium or at least a chaotic homeostasis!

But we digress. In DLP, the movement of the electrons and ions are responded to force-free aligned currents called “birkeland currents”⁸⁷, and other various plasma structures, modulated by the rules of pinching in magnetism. There is, nevertheless, a continuous ‘analog’ relationship between the streams. The alignment and circulation continues so long as the source voltages and neutrality is maintained, and there is no Exploding Double Layer (EDL) event⁸⁸.

Figure 7 - Synchrotron Radiation⁸⁹ Plasmod; credit: Dr. Anthony Peratt (JPL)

Again, if we can think of these structures as semi-permanent complex currents, they could perhaps guide us in a better engineering of national economies, by guiding our view of the currency interactions at “borders” of currencies as not so porous and monocular, so linear, structures.

Proposing the DLE

The DLE must conform to the DLP base physics, to remain consistent with the diagram in Figure 3. But it also must remain consistent with Figure 4! Therefore the idea is that there is a yin/yang like MIMS that has to be engineered. Here we must encounter a little biological and sociopolitical reality and pragmatism: people love physical mediums of money (like gold and cash) and are resistant to change. Those powerful on the false juice of fiat currencies (central bankers mostly, stock firms, private equity and hedge funds, etc.) and credit markets will also be highly resistant to changes not induced by Nature or war (probably war emergent from physics and nature, but potentially idealistic). Therefore, the author **does not recommend trying to**

⁸⁶ He is paraphrasing from H. Alfven’s text, “Double Layers and Circuits in Astrophysics,” May 1986

⁸⁷ <http://www.ptep-online.com/2015/PP-41-13.PDF>

⁸⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IEZk4tzt65U>

⁸⁹ <https://cds.cern.ch/record/398429/files/p437.pdf>

immediately switch from the following DLE to a more ideal, efficient, or truly decentralized DLE. It will be trouble to wean mankind off of the gluttony of breaking thermodynamics.⁹⁰

So how can DLE work, when there are so many nation-states to consider? Firstly, we must start with the need for an emergent process, and in emerging nations. Think: Africa, South America, Eastern Europe, Western Asia, Southeast Asia, and Oceania. These are places of tremendous population signal and more importantly: ambition. They are places where the people are flawed and this is good. The edge of chaos, not the middle of the field, produces the strongest gradient and evolution. At the edge of chaos the brain is most active. At the edge of breakdown are the potential seeds of change and revolution. This is where we should expect a rapid development signal, and the interest in newest MIMS infrastructures. It would be comparable to industrializing America of the mid 19th-20th century, or to London in the late 1800s, or China post 1990. India would also be a huge potential catalyst because while large they are multi-ethnic and also high IQ and a great number of wild-west type tech startups.

Secondly, aside from proper starting locations, there is a need for rigorous standardization. Again, we have that in a crypto MIMS architecture. The highly logical programmers will sort out the problems and mediate the spirit, mind, and will into a coded reality that can describe the process. All that remains is the understanding of the beneficent justice of the structure, rather than the hacker ethos: all for me, none for thee. Hackers learned this ethos from the current centralizing System, and as a consequence took to the Dark Web to practice social re-engineering and fell into social deconstructionism, despite the illogical nature of it.⁹¹

These “anonymous” types can be brought back (somewhat) into the system in the same self-interested way that they participate in building crypto layer architecture. Even a greedy hacker is curious how things work. In this way they can be co-opted into creating a dApp/DeFi compliant DLE architecture that is used by institutions as well as common people, just as TCP/IP was for the World Wide Web. TCP/IP emerged by the actions of a select few people, combining the streams of multiple sources: the U.S. Navy, academia, electronic engineers, IBM, etc., and mediating the largest MIMS ever created so far. But it is, of course, insufficient and becoming obsolete as it exposes poorly engineered areas that become anti-egalitarian, anti-freedom, anti-free-market (particularly Social Media and the so called FANGY⁹² control paradigm).

Figure 8 - 2 households in proposed DLE⁹³; credit: author

The test that is proposed is that two, then three households enact a similar infrastructure through a barter system, and then observe the human interactions, and record perhaps 10 such instances, and interview how it made people feel, and how goods and services moved

⁹⁰ Moreover, we know from the medicine that people, once diabetic, may never be wholly cured of a need for sweets. Similarly, those who were fattened on welfare, statism, and “social justice” programs which infected them with a lack of self-confidence and self-reliance, will probably be resistant to abandoning cynical hatred of: the rich, certain races they assume are better off for unfair reasons, Europeans, families, the religious, etc. They will probably have to be allowed to pass on bad ideas to offspring even ad infinitum until nature itself curtails unsuccessful genetic lines. Genocide of bad ideas (an extreme right response) by force is as bad as genocide of identities and individuals (an extreme left response).

⁹¹ In Die Hard 4, a hacker is at first impressed at the villains’ devious and perverted plan to destroy America’s infrastructure, until he sees the human cost of it. It was a very poignant portion of an otherwise dumb plot.

⁹² Facebook, Apple, Netflix, Google, Youtube

⁹³ Please bear in mind this is not a static proposal, and could be flip-flopped as needed, depending on goods, services, etc. The point is the field-like interaction!

between them, etc. Only through real world interactions can the proof of concept warrant the programming architecture to be built!

How can we test this? We ask that two households fastidiously follow this schema, and for a stipulated period of time, and we record the economic and sociological data before, during, and after. We then repeat this with at least 10 households. From there we add a third, then a fourth home, and track the data over a three year time period. It'd be important to have the homes involved interacting from all sorts of levels of economic class, from the poorest to the super rich if they can be found.

The idea being that if a household, which has financials and credit, can participate, and of course each has different needs and abilities, access and opportunities. This then would approximate the interface between nations. If the data is well recorded, and the architecture proved, then you move to a digital MIMS, probably a 4 layer such as cryptocurrency, and actually try the experiment again.

It may seem like a pipedream that such an experiment could filter up to massive economic engineering and design, but given the current pathway of the elite bankers and NGOs is to head towards destruction, they will be in need before 10 or 20 years have elapsed. They will have a need for a way to make the various nations of former Yugoslavia (for example) to get along economically if possible, politically if expedient. Think of the use for creating a buffer between African and Middle Eastern nations, war torn, so that they don't have to be weak or strong compared to each other but only internally. The MIMS guiding the DLE you could have the various layers be goods, commodities, bonds and other financial instruments, infrastructure deals, tax revenues, etc. The tuning of the values could be guided by an artificial intelligence which then automatically adjusts the values (voltages) and payment schedules (currency), to determine power interactions. Each country can therefore focus on strengthening its own internal DLE, and this will automatically modulate the entire analog system. This takes it from a wire diagram of X:Y currency ratios existing between every nation and behaving in a volatile manner, to a complex system of cellular modulation.

Figure 9 - World flight patterns, as analog of economic currency connections; credit: ESA⁹⁴

Such a wire diagram, while impressive and useful in describing the weakness of undeveloped nations' economies, belies a deeper problem. It's a nonlinear system, whose faults are now widely publicized. The COVID lockdown killed more people and children in these nations through starvation than COVID itself did! A

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https://www.esa.int/Enabling_Support/Space_Engineering_Technology/Proba_Missions/Proba-V_maps_world_air_traffic_from_space

simple wire of currency transaction is too full of tension, with no slack, and no ability to make easy adjustments. Problems in the mortgage market can bleed over into derivatives. Problems with the commodities whether they are oil, food, or minerals can easily become surges in the repo market. Bottlenecks in canals can create complexity problems in far flung markets. These markets seem like they have durability, resilience, and buffers, but in reality their only salvation is a growing debt market (derivatives primarily) now worth over \$1 quadrillion in estimated volume, far bigger than the total positive value of all the real estate in the world. What's worse is that when these markets melt down and debts come due, the only way to capture vaporized value is through Credit Default Swaps⁹⁵, which only firms with large amounts of money can afford, and not enough use, and most misuse. The Swaps market is now an unregulated bubble itself!

Instead, the economy should most definitely reflect a cellular design:

Figure 10 - plant cells of varying sizes; credit: 123RF

This is like having many anodes and cathodes, creating double layers between each other, repetitiously. The difference, of course, is that the cells of plasma - or in this case economies - will jiggle and be highly variable - with occasional “explosions” and “die offs” as there should be in terms of economic boom and bust. But at least there will be the same or similar cellular nutrient exchange as between living cells. Growth will be kept slow, but contraction will be sudden... and this is *good* because the needed rearrangements will be highly evolutionary, stimulating and anti-stagnating, and besides which vacuums will help push against monopolies by introducing sudden competition with rapid growth. Failing companies like Sears or General Motors would never be capable of continuing on in such a situation! This is *good*. As controlled forest fires promote new growth⁹⁶, so do repetitive failures in the capitalist economy. What harms this is unreasonable government welfarism (called subsidies), that prop up some companies, and not others... through bribery and corruption.

We need instead, in the author's opinion, to promote dynamism and buffering from sudden volatility. The “trapped” current can recycle the finances of the cells (nation states or even cities), and protect the cells from problems far away. It doesn't preclude rapid growth, either, but what it doesn't allow is that one or three nations be capable of trying to become gods of space while others purely starve... and when the former fail and crash the world economy the latter becomes not stronger but even weaker, and a famine that could rightly be called a genocide spread faster than pestulence! If a city wishes to outgrow its neighbors, or a state, etc. it can, but it has to fairly gather its voltage and value, while not destroying the currency of the neighbor. If it then proceeds to explode or contract, it also cannot drag down the neighbor. This is good!

Conclusions

Both concepts of the MIMS and DLE need vast amounts of exploration. On the one hand, we are beginning to live through times predicted in “Atlas Shrugged” where the misery of a few productive individuals is demanded for restitution for masses of less productive and individually self-centered ‘looters.’ On the other hand, relatively few individuals, increasing though their number may be, and increasing though the economic benefit of the world is, are in control of far too much centralized wealth, and this creates an unhealthy state of easy corruption, cronyism, and of course encourages the looters to lust for such wealth and power. The “Tao Te Ching” has said this long ago,

⁹⁵ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/creditdefaultswap.asp>

⁹⁶ <https://www.pbs.org/edens/yellowstone/shaped.html>

*“Better stop short than fill to the brim.
Oversharpen the blade, and the edge will soon blunt.
Amass a store of gold and jade, and no one can protect it.
Claim wealth and titles, and disaster will follow.
Retire when the work is done.
This is the way of heaven.”⁹⁷*

Therefore, the author thinks first and foremost, that for the masses of common people, elderly, children, and single parents, that it is imperative we understand the link between material security and wealth, and happiness and spiritual satisfaction. Not only of greed and envy, but also of simple household living.

Secondly, the author believes that the PEM or Force holds the key, both in terms of integrated connection to the Aether (Heaven), but also in terms of practicability vis-a-vis technologies like cryptocurrency, to the production of useful MIMS like Double Layer Economics. DLE’s could become local, next regional, then national and eventually international standards. Like the Internet, conquering not by force but necessity. The need is to deleverage, to eliminate fiat and its attempts to defy thermodynamics, and to recognize the growing threat in a complex world of un-recognized, unmitigated chaos and nonlinear dynamics. The next paper itself, in the philosophy series, shall deal with nonlinear dynamics, and refer back to the MIMS concept.

Epilogue

The avid EPEMC follower may be curious why the author strays into opinion articles⁹⁸, satirical Dark Matter papers⁹⁹, and now philosophy, martiality¹⁰⁰, strategy¹⁰¹, and economics¹⁰². The short answer, according to Figures 2 and 3, is that everything is connected. Or rather, everything is ‘wired’ together via the PEMF. In PEMC we focus upon the science of it... the *P* level of the powers so to speak. However, in Extended PEMC, the author wishes to explore subtler connections. In a previous paper the emergent property of theme parks was considered¹⁰³, after they emerged so soon historically to the creation of electric motors. In that paper, the connections to ancient motifs and archetypes was explored. However, the MIMS is implicitly present.

However, now one should consider the strategy and “shi” aspect. The Chinese concept of Shi is covered in the author’s works, elsewhere¹⁰⁴, as well as in “Propensity of Things” by F. Jullien. What does it have to do with EPEMC and with Derivatives meltdowns and currency wars?

⁹⁷ Tao Te Ching - Lao Tzu - chapter 9 <https://www.wussu.com/laotzu/laotzu09.html>

⁹⁸ Like

https://www.academia.edu/38759087/Opinion_Mars_Mission_Planning_is_Premature_Expensive_and_likely_Short_Sight_ed

⁹⁹ Like https://www.academia.edu/49497635/Converting_GNOME_CDM_Mass_Ratios_joke_paper

¹⁰⁰

https://www.academia.edu/49950881/Asymmetric_Vulnerabilities_of_the_US_and_New_Capabilities_in_Geopolitical_Warfare_Including_Economic_Digital_Cyberspatial_and_Lawfare

¹⁰¹

https://www.academia.edu/49950880/CALCULATING_THE_INNATE_SHI_%E5%8B%A2_OF_COUNTRIES_USING_THE_UNITED_STATES_OF_AMERICA_AS_A_TEMPLATE_1

¹⁰²

https://www.academia.edu/47732738/Simple_Guide_for_Friends_Family_and_Common_Folk_of_how_to_get_into_Crypto

¹⁰³

https://www.academia.edu/37403915/Ferris_Wheels_and_the_Dionysian_Irony_The_subconscious_drive_of_thrill_abandonment_of_caution_and_the_motifs_of_Amusement_Park_rides

¹⁰⁴ Such as https://www.academia.edu/40287817/Understanding_Chess_I_The_Art_of_Chess

The word currency should be the main key. Money flows, and electricity is treated as flowing water. There is however, a difference in the power equations in physics and finance/business:

$P = \frac{W}{dT} = V * I$ Equation for Power in physics, but $P = \frac{I}{R*t}$ in business or finance.

The point is that when considering flux, one of the 8 main principles or Laws in the P power, which is controlled by the PEM (F power) according to the Chinese metaphysicists and doctors, who observed the Wuxing from the south pole of Jupiter, which was displaying the Birkeland Current connections... one must consider the laws of thermodynamics. Particularly the idea of work upon oneself. It is a violation, whether in a linear or nonlinear dynamic.

Figure 11 - North and South Poles of Jupiter¹⁰⁵, showing the source of Chinese knowledge of fibonacci and the concepts of Bagua¹⁰⁶ and Wuxing, respectively; credit: Nature/Juno (NASA)

In terms of the MIMS, this is really key. In 2005 the world began noting the housing bubble¹⁰⁷. It did nothing. In 2007, Michael Burry made simple, easy to make (with some research¹⁰⁸) predictions based upon the propensity (inertia and momentum; Shi both) about the Mortgage Backed Securities¹⁰⁹ (especially CDOs¹¹⁰ and “synthetic” CDOs¹¹¹) meltdown. His choice was to pay insurance premiums on Credit Default Swaps¹¹², which then could be re-sold... if there were any banks solvent and with liquidity to buy them back. Over 1.5 years the situation worsened until the 2008 Mortgage Meltdown¹¹³

unfolded, taking AIG and Lehman Brothers banks down¹¹⁴. CDS values against Freddie Mac/Fannie Mae (which were subsequently nationalised¹¹⁵) went through the roof, and Burry made his investors a fortune despite (and in spite of) their ignorance. Mankind learned a valuable lesson about the dangers of CDOs and MBS, and other speculative financial instruments¹¹⁶. Right?

Wrong. Mankind did not learn¹¹⁷... any better than post Boxing Day tsunami¹¹⁸ where in 2018 another tsunami went undetected and killed thousands in the region of the Indian Ocean¹¹⁹ (where the magnetic poles are now accelerating towards¹²⁰). Mankind saw 230k people die, and did practically nothing¹²¹. So more died in an undetected night tsunami.

¹⁰⁵ Ibid. If the Hopewell had astute engineers based upon astronomical observations, the Chinese had 10x the efforts in the astronomical sciences, rivaled only by Babylonians and Egyptians and the Dogon.

¹⁰⁶ Lit: 8 trigrams; correlated by the author with the 8 Principles of the P power.

¹⁰⁷ <https://www.npr.org/templates/story/story.php?storyId=4679264>

¹⁰⁸ See: The “Big Short,” M. Lewis, 2010

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/m/mbs.asp>

¹¹⁰ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/cdo.asp>

¹¹¹ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/syntheticcdo.asp>

¹¹² <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/creditdefaultswap.asp>

¹¹³ <https://www.federalreservehistory.org/essays/subprime-mortgage-crisis>

¹¹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bankruptcy_of_Lehman_Brothers

¹¹⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Federal_takeover_of_Fannie_Mae_and_Freddie_Mac

¹¹⁶ <https://www.wsj.com/articles/in-a-blast-from-a-financial-crisis-past-synthetic-cdos-are-back-1503912601>

¹¹⁷ <https://knowledge.wharton.upenn.edu/article/cdos-are-back-will-they-lead-to-another-financial-crisis/>

¹¹⁸ <https://www.history.com/news/deadliest-tsunami-2004-indian-ocean>

¹¹⁹ <https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2018/10/02/world/asia/indonesia-tsunami-early-warning-system.html>

¹²⁰ <https://www.bbc.com/news/science-environment-52550973>

¹²¹ <https://www.cbsnews.com/news/tsunami-10-years-later-is-the-world-better-prepared-for-disaster/>

The author says this flatly: \$1 Quadrillion owed in derivatives is a far larger [potential¹²²] ‘megatsunami’ that will kill more people in nonlinear dynamical destruction than COVID or the Boxing Day tsunami ever could. If even 5% to 10% of CDOs (or “bespoke tranche opportunities” as they are called to keep them legal in the USA¹²³) were to go into default due to any excessive financial contagion¹²⁴ (perhaps hyperinflation?), then the entire complex MIMS known as the “financial services industry” and “central banking” would be at risk. Why? Violations of physics. The leverage created (via the power of numbers and of metaphysics - $N+P$ power) by derivatives relies upon fiat currencies.

Velocity of Money 1900-2020

Equation of Exchange: $M \cdot V = GDP$
annual

Source: Hoisington Investment Management

Figure 12 - Money Velocity 1900-2021; credit: Hoisington

Therefore, the author maintains that the need for a solution *like* DLE, based upon solid mimsical analysis and forward-thinking philosophy is absolutely **essential**, and was needed *yesterday*... let alone tomorrow.

But fiat velocity... is slowing down. Slowing down means decreased flux. Decreased flux plus more volatility¹²⁵ equates contagion in any medical/health context. If this MIMS breaks, however, the resulting ‘snapback’ (like a subduction earthquake but in the metaphysical space), would be megatsunami level. It would spread into socioeconomic geopolitics (SEGP) like a firestorm made of napalm and pyroclastic flow.

¹²² A balanced Rock may stay upon a point, until some impetus causes it to inevitably topple over. That is its predictable propensity (PP); the “rock smashing an egg” sentiment of Chinese Arts of War.

¹²³ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/b/bespoke-cdo.asp>

¹²⁴ Unknown to most people, in May 2021 the largest financial bubble (by total financial value, as measured by \$US) occurred when China arbitrarily decided to ban bitcoin mining. In 3 weeks, the market fell over \$2.3 trillion in value and continued a slide that continues as the author writes this. Crypto is a common hedge asset, and Bitcoin is known as digital gold to many investors. Yet, currently its value is still up more than the S&P 500 over the same 1 year period.

¹²⁵ Measured via the Dow Jones Stock Index and increasingly the cryptomarkets

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